

A Study on Artificial Intelligence in Financial Service

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence is defined as ‘Intelligent Agents’ and sometimes called as ‘Machine Intelligence’, it is an intelligence demonstrated by machines in contrast to natural intelligence displayed by humans. Nowadays, Artificial Intelligence is playing a major role in the financial service industries and taking it into higher peak. It helps companies in financial industry to save time, reduce costs and add value through the usage of algorithms that generate insights, acting as filtering key information which makes human work more effective and easy from wide variety of sources. It also helps in managing the trading decisions by processing the data and creating algorithms to manage trade better. It is useful to bank sectors as well, that helps in serving the customers efficiently by predicting and reducing the risk quickly. It also detects fraud or false information provided in data that humans might miss and reduces false declines. Artificial Intelligence has countless applications in financial service ecosystem that are prepared to transform the industry in the next several years including detecting and analysing brand sentiments, providing investment insights, making banking more efficient and less risky and identifying fraud etc. This paper is an attempt to analyse the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Financial Services. It is purely based on secondary source i.e. obtained from blogs, journals, magazines, newspapers etc.

Keywords: Detects Fraud, Less Risky, Machine Intelligence, Intelligent Agent, Filters Information, Analyses Brand Sentiments, Artificial Intelligence Algorithms.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence was first introduced in 1956 where many scientists from variety of fields like mathematics, psychology, engineering, economics, politics etc. came up with new creativity of intelligence i.e., artificial brain which is sometimes called as machine intelligence. It is a type of artificial intelligence where a machine uses to demonstrate any task given in financial institutions accurately compared to natural intelligence of human. Artificial Intelligence reduces the stress of a common man and also enhances the activities of companies efficiently by using various sources like algorithms, detecting frauds, security, good customer service etc. which helps people to keep their good financial stability. Artificial Intelligence techniques usually help in solving the challenging problems of financial companies. Many financial companies data will be structured or unstructured taken from different source of different quality will also influence the artificial intelligence in many ways

which should address unique task performance. The future of finance will be heavily influenced by financial companies like Financial Technology (FinTech) to increase the level of competition for generating revenue by using maximum resources, algorithms and many others in various fields like trading, investing, banking, lending etc.

Objectives

- To know the role of Artificial Intelligence in financial service.
- To analyse the present and future applications of Artificial Intelligence in financial service.
- To know the challenges of Artificial Intelligence in financial service.

Research Methodology

This paper is empirical in nature and it is purely based on secondary source i.e., obtained from newspapers, blogs, magazines, journals which reports that it is based on actual observations.

Review of Literature

- Paul Dravis- ‘Artificial Intelligence in Finance’ The Road Ahead, Harvard Business Review, and artificial intelligence reshapes the work of human effectively in financial structure.
- Kul Bhushan- Artificial Intelligence in Banking: Challenges and Opportunities, technology cannot be implemented without challenges and opportunities, Artificial Intelligence in India especially in banking is not going to be considered without challenges which is beyond chat-bots.
- Ryoji Kashiwagi- Utilisation of Artificial Intelligence in Finance, financial Information Technology marketing department, wake of technological innovation known as deep learning in Artificial Intelligence is being utilised in various forms more actively as open innovation.

What is the Role of Artificial Intelligence in Financial Service Sector?

Artificial intelligence plays a major role in financial sectors and enhances financial companies workforce effectively from algorithmic trading to fraud detection which helps in saving time, minimising risks, earning money and also minimises the risk of human’s accuracy.

Enhancing Customer Engagement: Once, financial service industry didn’t pay attention to the quality of personalised communications and Artificial Intelligence technologies made this possible by developing its knowledge. Nowadays, in Artificial Intelligence there are algorithms based portfolio and natural language processes that help financial advisors to provide accurate guidelines to the customers or investors based on their financial queries.

Accelerating Fraud Detection and Minimizing Risk: Financial companies from many years are dependent on Artificial Intelligence in detecting frauds or false information that reduces the risk of companies effectively and starts growing up. Many companies such as ‘MasterCard13’, ‘ThetaRay’ offer a platform to detect frauds such as lending frauds in their financial institutions.

Maximise Resources: In Artificial Intelligence, by the usage of maximum resources like algorithms generating insights, enhancing customer service and predicting company’s activities like sales will help many companies in financial industry in saving time and money.

Unlocking the Value of Algorithms: It is software containing automated tasks like matching data records, making elimination and calculations in financial sectors. Artificial Intelligence is built to learn and improve so that, companies can access to the large data sets to unlock the value of Artificial Intelligence algorithms. There are three types of data that Artificial Intelligence handles

i.e.,

- Parameters and Numbers that generate insights.
- Analyzing, Interpreting and Writing Text using natural language which is processing with Artificial Intelligence.
- Images that detect patterns, activity, object recognition, etc. which can be done only by using learning methods of Artificial Intelligence.

Trading: Better Trading through Algorithms: Many financial or investment firms have adopted algorithms for trading through sentiments or insights from social media, news or any other sources of data. It usually helps in managing trading rules and decisions through algorithms, customer service, and sentiment analysis and so on.

Filtering Information and Analysing Sentiments: Artificial Intelligence filters information received from wide variety of sources and provides useful data that help companies to improve their efficiency in workplace. For example, Reuters News Tracer, filters key information through artificial intelligence algorithms i.e., artificial intelligence filters only those important data which is useful before reporting it. Similarly, financial service companies detect sentiment from social media that provides useful advice with the help of artificial intelligence.

Banking: Artificial Intelligence enhances Efficiency, offers Data Insights, and Manage Risks: Artificial Intelligence enhances companies efficiency through chatbots that provides customer service efficiently and solves queries, listens to customers call, and provides accurate advice. Many financial firms contains unstructured database which stores information separately in entities where financial firms takes complete advantage of artificial intelligence to manage risks and work effectively.

Image Recognition in Financial Technology: Recent developments in machine learning have increased image recognition accuracy level that exceeds human capacity where 'Confirm.io' automatically identifies the data of consumer identity, and 'Onfido's platform' provides large database that is related to public which may include the verification of employee's identity or background data of criminal records.

Artificial Intelligence in Finance- Present and Future Applications

Today machine learning has come to play an integral role in many phases of the financial ecosystems from approving loans to managing assets. Yet few technically, some professionals have an accurate view of just how many ways machine learning finds its way into their daily financial lives.

Machine Learning in Finance- Current Applications

Below are some examples used wisely today in machine learning. These applications are applied currently in finance that generates good financial stability.

Portfolio Management: In artificial intelligence system, robo-advisors are the algorithms built to standardize financial portfolio. The advisors guide investors in investing on various financial investment fields. It is earning money by investing in various assets based on different investments.

Algorithmic Trading: It is a process programmed in computers to follow set of instructions for placing a trade in order to generate profits faster which is impossible for human traders. It is also known as automated trading system which uses complex artificial intelligence system to make faster trading decisions.

Fraud Detection: In machine learning, nowadays there are new tactics applied in detecting fraud through learning actively in identifying threats that take place in investments, lending or security in finance which human's might miss. It also minimises the risk of misleading information of a firm.

Machine Learning in Finance- Future Applications

The applications applied above are actively taken place today and also some are established for considering in future. Below are some applications applied in future,

Customer Service: Chatbots are the main source in customer service which is an artificial intelligence that conducts conversation. Nowadays, companies like ‘Kasisto’ are adopting chatbots to solve the common queries of customers in financial issues. These are built in natural language processing engine that interacts with customers especially in finance.

Security: Applications which are currently developed and used in frauds in financial or banking field needs to be secured and usernames, passwords or any security questions doesn’t influence on user’s security much where in future, securities might be advance that contain facial recognition or voice recognition or other data for safety.

Sentiment/News Analysis: It is supposed to be applied in future applications of artificial intelligence that extracts subjective information from social media, news trends or any other data source to identify the unstructured data i.e., trying to understand the price fluctuations or customers requirements in business intelligence.

Relevant Companies that comes under Artificial Intelligence Financial Service

Below is the shortlist of organizations come under these application areas,

- Portfolio Management- Betterment, Schwab Intelligent Portfolios
- Algorithmic Trading- Renaissance Technologies, Walnut Algorithms
- Fraud Detection- Kount, APEX Analytix
- Customer Service- Kasisto
- Security- FaceFirst, Cognitec
- Sentiment/News Analysis- Hearsay Social

Challenges of Artificial Intelligence in Financial Services

In financial institutions, artificial intelligence tends to create secure decisions for providing benefits to the banks applied in financial field. As in artificial intelligence decisions and initiatives takes place challenges also overcomes.

Understanding Artificial Intelligence and its Implications: For any financial firms, understanding artificial intelligence is the biggest challenge before implementing it. Artificial intelligence in financial firms plays a very important role and the benefits that occur from artificial intelligence should be knowledgeable for financial firms.

Data Quality: Every financial institution knows that data is important for success and many critical situations arise as challenge in firms through data quality issues. As the level of data grows as per time and effort applied for collection of data then the quality of data should also be standardized which is based on intelligent algorithm.

Narrow Focus: Intelligent algorithms are good at solving specific problems but they are poor in emotional intelligence and don’t contextualise the information in which human’s can only handle. An intelligent algorithm is trained to detect only specific payments in trade and not their specific activities which sometimes create barriers in banks or finance.

Responsibility: In the usage of artificial intelligence, challenges would be faced in terms of any responsibility taken place and especially in those cases when anything goes wrong during the process who shall take its responsibility. A financial institution foresees the activities of machine under the supervision of human and tries to allocate it accurately.

Suggestions

- The first step is to identify the problem clearly whether it exists or not before finding its solution so that the conflicts could not arise in the future for employment i.e., securing in advance.
- One should be aware of the functions of machine intelligence and need to explain each and every process or plans that take place in artificial intelligence before applying it in financial society.
- Artificial Intelligence should be more focused in communication and other developments for the sake of financial service according to the regulations applied on it strictly for providing data.

Conclusions

Artificial Intelligence in financial service industry has been changing and about 10% of organisations started to adopt artificial intelligence to compete and identify opportunities that human's might miss. Artificial Intelligence is very less in percentage for organisations but by gaining knowledge related to its benefits many companies start to adopt and work on it. It is a source which helps in company's progress and it provides value to the artificial intelligence responsibilities for applying it into future technologies.

The creation of Artificial Intelligence is huge in cost and also doesn't contain any emotions but it helps in reducing the error in the data and also helps in making corrections as many as possible repetitively. It doesn't take any break unlike humans while processing data and also contributes its artificial brain completely in various fields like medical, social, political and financial.

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